

“A Study of children's Perception of Parenting and Aggression of Secondary School Students”

Manorama Singh¹, Dr. Neetu Singh²

¹Research Scholar, Faculty of Education, Dayalbagh Educational Institute,
(Deemed University), Dayalbagh, Agra 282005

²Supervisor, Faculty of Education, Dayalbagh Educational Institute,
(Deemed University), Dayalbagh, Agra 282005

Corresponding Author- Manorama Singh

Abstract-

The researcher has studied this for the purpose that in today's era, children rarely consider the teachings of their parents. If their parents talk about understanding, then they feel that they are imposing restrictions on us. If you scold them a little, then they feel insulted. So, is it the effect of parenting, is it the reason why children are becoming more aggressive in nature, the researcher tried to **find out the relationship between these two variables**. Using **'Descriptive survey method'** has been used in the present research study. In the presented research paper, **the students of inter college located in Agra metropolis have been selected, only 11th and 12th students. 100 students (50 Boys-50 Girls) of secondary level have been selected in this research paper.** Use of the Research tools- **The scale prepared by Dr. Anand Pyari and Rajkumari Kalra (2010) has been used to measure the Children's Perception of Parenting of students and To measure the aggressiveness of the students, the scale made by Dr. Guru Pyari Mathur and Dr. Raj Kumar Kalra Bhatnagar (2004) has been used.** Standardized tools have been used for hypothesis testing in the research paper. For this Research paper- **mean, standard deviation, product moment correlation and t-test** have been used to test the hypothesis. It was found during it can be said that there is a **significant difference in the Children's Perception of Parenting of secondary school boys and girls** and there is a **significant difference in the Aggression of secondary school boys and girls.** it can be said **that there is a low positive correlation relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression of secondary school boys and there is a very high positive correlation relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression of secondary school boys.**

Keywords: - Children's Perception of Parenting, Aggression and Secondary School Students.

Introduction:

It is widely held that parental involvement plays a key role in enhancing student engagement, but less is known about whether and how children's Perception of Parenting and their Aggression. Different types of parental involvement relate to dimensions of student engagement. **Clinical psychologist Seema Hingorrany, says, “With the increased exposure, the IQ (Intelligence Quotient) of children and teens is on the rise but EQ (Emotional Quotient) is on the decline as their emotional needs are not being addressed by their near and dear ones.”** In most cases, teens suffer from anger issues when either one parent or both parents have had a history of anger. Factors such as nagging, abusing and being compared to other kids in the family also have a huge impact on a child's mental state. The concept of aggression falls into two categories: instrumental aggression and hostile aggression. While instrumental aggression is used to accomplish an objective or purpose, hostile aggression is intended to hurt others and involves two types of overt aggression (physical and verbal) and social aggression.

Children's Perception of Parenting:-

In the present study, the researcher for the purpose of recording Children's Perception of

Parenting used Children's Perception of Parenting Scale (CPPS). According to the scale Children's Perception of Parenting can be defined as the sum total of the score obtained by the Child in six different types of area based - 1. Democratic 2. Autocratic 3. Accepting 4. Rejecting 5. Over Protecting & 6. Over Demanding.

Aggression:

In children and adolescents, violence is the most According to **Johnson (1972), aggression is “physical or verbal behaviour that is intended to hurt someone”.**

Coi and Dogde (2000), defined as **“Any behaviour intended to harm an individual who is motivated to avoid being harmed.”** It can be concluded at that aggression is a behaviour, which indulges an individual to hurt others either verbally or physically for his own sake to satisfy his desires.

This study deepens our understanding of the dynamic interplay between children's Perception of Parenting and Aggression. Along with the increase of knowledge in the students of secondary level, the development of social virtues is done only through education, even education is the knowledge of their rights and duties in the students, awareness of national unity and integrity, self-reliance and development of character qualities.

Review of Related Literature:-

1. It was done by **Toslina Sultana Begum (2018)**, them in Barpeta district of Assam, located in North East India. In this study on **“Perception of parents and adolescents on parenting: A sociocultural study”** 200 adolescents in the age group of 16 to 17 years were selected as a sample. Self-made equipment has been used in this study, researches reveal that positive and negative outcomes of adolescents are dependent on parenting style applied to them.
 2. A research work done by **Kaur, S. (2019)**, on **“Aggression among adolescents in relation to family climate”** 100 boys and 100 girls of class X. Descriptive survey method has been used in this research work and according to the conclusion of this study it has been found that the aggression and aggression of boys of class X There is a positive correlation between family environment and a negative correlation between aggression and family environment in class X girls.
 3. **“The study of anxiety and aggression between rural and urban female sports students”** of research work by **Blugude, B.A. (2021)**, In this study, 60 female (30 rural and urban) school students were taken as a sample, they were 17 to 21 years old. The standarized psychological tools, Dr. Ram Ashish Singh for measurement of anxiety and the scale made by Prof. D.N. Srivastava was used for aggression measurement. The result that there is no difference in the anxiety as well as in the aggression of rural and urban female sport students. The result also there is a positive and significant correlation between anxiety and aggression of rural and urban female sport students.
 4. A research paper **“A study of aggression adolescents”** by **Thakur, S. (2021)**, a descriptive study was conducted to explore the relationship between aggression and family environment among adolescents. A sample consisting of 200 adolescents was taken from the three districts of Punjab state namely Ludhiana, Sangrur and Hoshiarpur. Data was collected with the help of Aggression Scale by Dr. G.P.Mathur and Dr. Raj Kumar Bhatnagar (2012) and Family Environment Scale by Dr. Harpreet Bhatia and Dr. N.K. Chadha (2015). Subsequently data was subjected to statistical analysis. Results clearly indicated a significant relationship between overall aggression and family environment of adolescent students.
 5. The study by **East Chinese Yong, J. and other (2022)**, this topic is **“Parents’ perception or children’s perception? Parental involvement and student engagement in Chinese middle schools”** students and their parents from surveying 2219 of secondary schools, found that some types of parental involvement, rather than parental involvement, were correlated with student dimensions.
 6. This research study was conducted by **Maria Giulia Olivari (2015)**, research on **“Adolescent Perceptions of Parenting Styles in Sweden, Italy and Greece: An Exploratory Study.”** The purpose of this research study was to examine the similarities and differences in retrospective perceptions of adolescent parenting. This research study was conducted on parents from Sweden, Italy and Greece. The dimensions of parenting have been examined such as mother's role, adolescent gender, country of origin, etc. Under this method of peace ANOVA was used and in this, mothers were considered more authoritative than fathers, contribution to parenting styles literature, showing how country legislation concerning family matters and SES are related the perception of parenting behaviours.
- Statement of Problem:** - “A Study of children's Perception of parenting and Aggression of Secondary School Students”
- Objectives of the Study:-**
1. To comparative study of children's perception of parenting of secondary school boys and girls.
 2. To comparative study of aggression of secondary school boys and girls.
 3. To study the relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression in secondary school boys.
 4. To study the relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression in secondary school girls.
- Hypothesis of the Study:-**
1. There would be no significant difference in the children's perception of parenting of secondary school boys and girls.
 2. There would be no significant difference in the aggression of secondary school boys and girls.
 3. There would be no significant relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression in secondary school boys.
 4. There would be no significant relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression in secondary school girls.

Research Methods:-

‘Descriptive survey method’ has been used in the present research study.

Delimitations of Research Study:-

- In the presented research paper, the students of inter college located in Agra metropolis have been selected.
- Only 11th and 12th students have been selected in this research paper.

Selection of Sampling:- In the research study, 100 students of secondary school (50 boys and 50 girls) have been selected.

Variables:-

Independent Variables: - Secondary School Students.

Dependent Variable: - Children's Perception of Parenting and Aggression.

Use of the Research tools:-

1. The scale prepared by Dr. Anand Pyari and Rajkumari Kalra (2010) has been used to measure the Children's Perception of Parenting of students.
2. To measure the aggressiveness of the students, the scale made by Dr. Guru Pyari Mathur and Dr. Raj Kumar Kalra Bhatnagar (2004) has been used.

Statistical Method used for Research Study:-

Mean, Standard Deviation, Product Moment Correlation and t-test.

Results and Interpretation:-

1. **To comparative study of children's perception of parenting of secondary school boys and girls.**

Table No. - 1 Details of children's perception of parenting of secondary school boys and girls.

Variable	Sample	n	Mean	SD	t-test	Significant level
Children's perception of parenting	Boys	50	141.08	12.34	2.96	Significant
	Girls	50	132.74	15.62		

Interpretation:-

The value of **t-2.96** calculated in the presented **table No.-1** is more than both 0.05 and 0.01 level for **df = 98**, so it has been found significant. Null hypothesis **“There would be no significant difference in the perception of**

children towards parenting of secondary school boys and girls” is rejected. Therefore, it can be said that there is a significant difference in the children's perception of parenting of secondary school boys and girls.

2. **To comparative study of aggression of secondary school boys and girls.**

Table No. - 2 Details of aggression of secondary school boys and girls.

Variable	Sample	n	Mean	SD	t-test	Significant level
Aggression	Boys	50	173.26	12.97	4.01	Significant
	Girls	50	186.68	19.84		

Interpretation:-

The value of **t-4.01** calculated in the presented **table No.-2** is more than both 0.05 and 0.01 level for **df = 98**, so it has been found significant. Null hypothesis **“There would be no**

significant difference in the aggression of secondary school boys and girls.” is rejected. Therefore, it can be said that there is a significant difference in the aggression of secondary school boys and girls.

1. **Diagram:** - To comparison study of children's Perception of Parenting and Aggression of Secondary School Students boys and girls.

3. **There would be no significant relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression in secondary school boys.**

Table No.-3 Details of obtained scores of correlation between children's perception of parenting and aggression in secondary school boys.

Variable (Boys)	n	Mean	S.D.	df	r	Significance ρ (rho)	Effect of size
Children's perception parenting	50	141.08	12.33	98	0.45	18.49	0.20
Aggression	50	173.26	12.97				

Interpretation:-

Presented in **table No.-3**. For **df-98**, at 0.05 and 0.01 level, the calculated value of **ρ -18.49** is more than the table values of both 1.66 and 2.36, so it is significant. Null hypothesis **“There would be no significant relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression in secondary school boys” is rejected**. Therefore, it

can be said that there is a low positive correlation relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression of secondary school boys.

4. There would be no significant relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression in secondary school girls.

Table No. - 4 Details of obtained scores of correlation between children's perception of parenting and aggression in secondary school girls.

Variable (Girls)	n	Mean	S.D.	df	r	Significance ρ (rho)	Effect of size
Children's perception parenting	50	132.74	15.61	98	0.98	70.97	0.96
Aggression	50	186.68	19.84				

Interpretation:-

Presented in **table No. - 4**. For **df-98**, at 0.05 and 0.01 level, the calculated value of **ρ -70.96** is more than the table values of both 1.66 and 2.36, so it is significant. Null hypothesis **“There would be no significant relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression in secondary school girls” is rejected**. Therefore, it can be said that there is a very high positive correlation relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression of secondary school boys.

perception of parenting and aggression of secondary school boys.

Importance of Research Study:-

- The parents and teachers must identify-appreciate and emotionally support intelligence in the students in a proper way. This will enable them to know, understand and manage their aggression and it will help them to live a happy life later.
- Parents and teachers should teach emotional defence to the children.
- Parents should try their best to understand the needs, motives and urges of their children and help them to channelize their energy in positive actions.

Suggestions for Further Research:

- Similar study can be conducted on a large sample.
- This research paper can also be done on other districts.
- Research work can also be done at more academic levels.
- Children's Perception of Parenting among adolescents in relation to personality.
- Children's Perception of Parenting among adolescents in relation to socio-economic status.
- Aggression among adolescents in relation to school climate.

Bibliography:

- Archer, J. & Coyne, S.M. (2005) “An integrated review of indirect, relational and social aggression.” *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 9, 212-230.
- Chauhan, S.S. (1978) *Advanced Educational Psychology*. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House.
- Mangal, S.K. (2006) *Advanced Educational Psychology*, Prentice Hall India, New Delhi.

Findings from Research Studies:-

1. Null hypothesis **“There would be no significant difference in the perception of children towards parenting of secondary school boys and girls” is rejected**. Therefore, it can be said that there is a significant difference in the Children's Perception of Parenting of secondary school boys and girls.
2. Null hypothesis **“There would be no significant difference in the aggression of secondary school boys and girls.” is rejected**. Therefore, it can be said that there is a significant difference in the Aggression of secondary school boys and girls.
3. Null hypothesis **“There would be no significant relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression in secondary school boys” is rejected**. Therefore, it can be said that there is a low positive correlation relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression of secondary school boys.
4. Null hypothesis **“There would be no significant relationship between children's perception of parenting and aggression in secondary school girls” is rejected**. Therefore, it can be said that there is a very high positive correlation relationship between children's

- Mathur, G. P. and Bhatnagar, R.K. (2004) to measure the aggressiveness scale of the students.
- Pyari, A.K. (2010) Manual for Children's Perception of Parenting Scale, Rakhi Prakashan, Agra.
- Sharma, S., & Singh, S. (2010) "A study of perceived fathering and mothering in relation to aggression among adolescents." *Journal of Indian Psychological Review*, 74 (4), 241-246.
- Somal, R. (2008) "Relationship between friendship, aggression and self-esteem. *Praachi Journal of Psycho-Cultural Dimensions*, 24 (1), 64-68.